

MEDICAL BIOLOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PREPARATION OF THE MOST HIGHLY QUALIFIED SPORES.

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Annotation.

The article includes diagnostic analysis, training in elite sports and rehabilitation and recovery technologies in the performance of competitive physical work. Practical recommendations were made on the organization of the medical and biological provision of highly qualified athletes. The participation of institutions and organizations of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other relevant organizations in solving this problem is a matter of tasks.

Keywords.

sports, innovative technologies, training process, recovery, functional systems, metabolic processes, vegetative indicators.

The training of highly qualified athletes is a complex multifactorial process based on a very kata methodology of physical education, the practice of the educational process and modern achievements of biomedical science. The importance of biomedical assistance in the training of highly qualified athletes has increased significantly in recent times among the world's leading sports countries (USA, China, Germany, France, Scandinavian countries, etc.), which is objectively associated with effective management of the training process and a significant increase in sports results.

These states were formed, and during their activities, the scientifically based concept of the active impact of biomedical tools on the athlete's recovery processes was carried out, carrying out large-scale, intensive training and competitive work

A well-functioning system of scientific-practical and medico-biological provision of highly qualified athletes; covers a wide range of professional issues. Attracting many specialized scientific and clinical institutions of the Medical Academy with the account Ministry of Sciences and health (more than 62 organizations), the system of medical and biological provision of training highly qualified athletes had a strong scientific and material and technical base. This system was unified by the state management-led organizational structure medical-

biological provision of training of national teams of the country, which in its work relied on problematic issues related to the interagency Scientific Council of the Academy of Sports Medicine and Medical Sciences. commissions responsible for mass physical education and Olympic affairs have been successful in rebuilding sports

Through complex scientific groups on the types of scientific and practical and medical and biological supplies with the formed state system, sport effectively solved the tasks of introducing academic achievements into the educational practice of children's and adolescent sports schools, Olympic Reserve sports schools and higher sports skills schools, as well as training highly qualified athletes of national teams.

The properly organized learning process is a long-term complex of physiological stimuli aimed at almost all functional systems. With a large volume and high intensity of work performed, physical education causes sharp disturbances in the body and activates compensatory shifts: both in terms of an immediate response to physical activity and in terms of a long-term subsequent effect. The absence of medical-biological control and the incorrect structure of training occurs decompensation, accompanied by a decrease in the process, energy and plastic structures, mechanisms associated with excessive activation of muscles in the body, which, as a rule, taxilize the activity of the enzymatic, secretory and nervous systems. Due to this, these physiological shifts in the educational process should not exceed the body's ability to adapt, since they can lead to a violation of compensatory mechanisms. Disorders of physiological functions and a high level of trauma are felt.

At the same time, in order to improve special performance, a new physiological level, the intensity of training loads should approach the limit of adaptation opportunities. It has been scientifically proven that physical loads close to the limit, which are repeated only a few times, increase the functionality of the physiological systems of the body that provide this physical work. Thus, biomedical control of physiological changes is the main condition for the correct Organization of the educational process. However, it is possible only when there is a scientifically based complex of diagnostic methods and a complex of functional tests that objectively assess the changes in Vegetative indicators and metabolic processes that occur in the body as a result of training and competitive activities. It is necessary to analyze and take into account not only the training and competition activities of athletes, but also their recovery period, since during the recovery period a complex of the most active physiological processes is formed in the body,

adaptive and morphofunctional shifts. adaptive systems of the body that provide support-movement, in a particular sport, a new physiological level of activity is carried out.

In recent years, advances in the development of the theory of functional systems have given sports medicine specialists a new means of determining the "physiological cost" of the training process, aimed at sports results. Such an approach allows you to plan the educational process on a scientific basis, eliminate the health-threatening transcendental activation of the physiological systems of the athlete's body. Specially developed use indicated biological, immune-hormonal and other physiological tests make it possible to predict the nature, intensity and duration of vegetative and metabolic reactions and thus assess the level of physical performance and the behavior of the whole organism in stressful and extreme situations, for example, at a high level. - intensive sports training and especially competitions. At the same time, in sports, when using physiological methods, an individual approach to a particular athlete is required. Diagnostics, biochemical tests, a system of functional tests and downloads, an assessment of the state of fitness, all this is the basis of effective management of athlete training in order to ensure high sports performance in the process of training and competition activities.

It has been scientifically proven that in each sport, in each sports discipline, there are physical and specific characteristics. Functional training, which determines achievements, is the high sports results that must be achieved in training and carried out in sports competitions. Studying humoral and hormonal mechanisms (sympathoadrenal system, blood cholinergic system, corticosteroids, etc.), as well as vegetative regulation of sports, activity allows you to effectively control the process of training highly qualified athletes. By changing the components of physical activity, you will be able to purposefully influence a certain functional system of the body, mobilize the necessary physiological processes, energize the intensive activity of muscles and bring homeostasis of the internal environment, almost any level and direction of physiological reactions, thereby ensuring the achievement of the desired training result. the intensity of training loads, the expected volume of training, in which the greatest increase is observed and the ability to work is achieved.

Different stages and periods of training highly qualified athletes:

Currently, training complexes are widely used to train highly qualified athletes in the training process, which allow one-time processing of time characteristics and energy costs for the bot performed at different stages of the

training process. The role of biomedical tests in the body is changing, but different models are being built.

The training load mode allows you to objectively control the physiological state of the functional system of the body with continuous monitoring with feedback, which opens up completely new scientifically based opportunities for managing training processes aimed at sports results.

In the sport of the highest achievements during the training process and subsequent recovery, the performance and intensity of large-scale training loads, a large number of physiotherapeutic procedures, biomedical technologies and technical means are used, which make it possible to restore the performance of athletes at short intervals. Such technologies, widely used by our competitors, as well as developed by US and recommended in the process of training highly qualified athletes, include:

- external contrapulsation as a means of recovery and improving sports performance in elite sports.

- electrolaser myostimulation method, which not only improves physical performance, but also gives high efficiency in existing rehabilitation and regenerative and therapeutic activities.

- method of rehabilitation and recovery with the help of heat-cold treatments and vitamin complexes, the method of acclimatization has a pronounced restorative effect increases the physical performance of highly qualified athletes

- optional hypoxic ventilation training functions are based on changes in External breathing and gas exchange breathing form, breathing frequency and depth, as well as minute breathing volume. The proposed method is that the stability of the function of external respiration and gas exchange by increasing hypoxia leads to an increase in resistance to Vegetative and motor hypoxia.

Previous experience has shown that the active participation of specialists in academic sciences of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan allows new innovative biomedical technologies to bring the training of highly qualified athletes to a new scientifically based level in the short term.

In modern sports with the highest achievements, the result of sports is ensured by its own flexible changes in everything. Functional systems of the body, which form new metabolic capabilities of the body, provide training and competitive activities of athletes. In this regard, the problem of biomedical technologies in elite sports, raised by the authors, is undoubtedly timely, socially significant and relevant.

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